

Salmonella Control Programme - Results for the year 2014

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As part of the EU-wide salmonella control programme, the member states draw up an annual report on the proportion of *Salmonella*-positive flocks of breeding poultry (*Gallus gallus*), laying hens, broilers as well as breeding and fattening turkeys. To compile the national report, the federal states have been submitting their investigation results to the competent federal authorities for evaluation since 2007. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) prepares the report on the control programme every year on the basis of this data.

The evaluation of the data for 2014 shows a frequency of *Salmonella* occurrences (prevalence) similar to or slightly less than last year's level among breeding hens, laying hens, breeding turkeys and fattening turkeys, but an increase in the detection rate with broilers.

Where the control-relevant serovars are concerned, the communal target value was achieved for all categories of commercial poultry considered in the control programmes. A prevalence of under 1% for the control-relevant serovars was achieved for breeding hens, laying hens, broilers, breeding turkeys and fattening turkeys.

The full version of this BfR opinion is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/salmonella-bekaempfungsprogramm-ergebnisse-fuer-das-jahr-2014.pdf>